
THE ROLE OF THE INTERNATIONAL COMMUNITY IN THE WAR BETWEEN PALESTINE AND ISRAEL

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ABSTRACT

The conflict between Israel and Palestine is a longstanding and complex geopolitical issue rooted in historical, religious, and territorial disputes. The origins of the conflict can be traced back to the late 19th and early 20th centuries when Zionist and other national movements gained momentum in the area. However, the conflict of interest has turned brutal off- late with a lot of casualties in terms of human death, destruction of religious places and destruction of a life time.

Keywords: Conflict, death, destruction, war, politics

I. INTRODUCTION

Palestine, located in the Middle East, persists of two main areas: the West Bank and the Gaza Strip. The West Bank shares borders with Israel, Jordan, and the Dead Sea, on the other hand Gaza Strip is situated between Egypt, Israel, and the Mediterranean Sea. Roughly half of the West Bank is under Israeli administration, while the Palestinian government oversees the remaining portion. The Gaza Strip operates independently.

The aggression between Israelis and Palestinians originated in the late nineteenth century. In 1947, the United Nations approved Resolution 181, commonly referred to as the Partition Plan, aiming to split the British Mandate of Palestine into separate Arab and Jewish states. On May 14, 1948, the establishment of the State of Israel occurred, leading to the onset of the first Arab-Israeli War. Despite Israel emerging victorious in 1949, the conflict resulted in the displacement of 750,000 Palestinians, and the territory was subsequently divided into three parts: the State of Israel, the West Bank (along the Jordan River), and the Gaza Strip.

In the subsequent years, tensions escalated in the region, particularly among Israel, Egypt,

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Jordan, and Syria. After the 1956 Suez Crisis and Israel's incursion into the Sinai Peninsula, Egypt, Jordan, and Syria entered into mutual defence agreements in anticipation of a potential Israeli military mobilization. In June 1967, following a series of strategic moves by Egyptian President Abdel Gamal Nasser, Israel launched a preemptive strike against the air forces of Egypt and Syria, marking the beginning of the Six-Day War. Following the conflict, Israel gained control over the Sinai Peninsula and Gaza Strip from Egypt, the West Bank and East Jerusalem from Jordan, and the Golan Heights from Syria.

Coming to the latest thing, On Oct 7, 2023 Hamas launched an offensive on Israel because of the years of atrocities committed by them towards Palestine. Hamas launched a deadly attack on Israel by firing rockets and storming the cities and towns of Israel.² Moreover, they took hundreds of hostages with them and the Hamas gunmen killed civilians and soldiers in their homes, at a music festival, and on the streets.³

In a response to this attack, Israel retaliated by airstrikes against Gaza and announced a “Complete siege” of the territory that would deprive it of incoming supplies of food, water and fuel. Israel also assembled tens of thousands of troops to invade Gaza, with Prime Minister Benjamin Netanyahu of Israel vowing to “demolish” Hamas.

The phone and internet services went down in Gaza amid a massive aerial and artillery bombardment — and Israeli armies advanced into the north part of the country. Since the past three days, Israel has expanded its ground operations, though the extent of their activities inside Gaza remain ambiguous.

The number of civilians killed in Gaza has exceeded 5,000 death tolls according to the sources and the number still keeps rising.⁴ UNRWA reported that approximately 600,000 internally displaced individuals are taking refuge in a total of 150 UNRWA facilities, with nearly 420,000 seeking shelter in 93 facilities located in the Middle, Khan Younis, and Rafah areas in the southern region. This reflects an increase of approximately 14,000 civilians in the past 24 hours.

² <https://www.nytimes.com/2023/11/12/world/middleeast/israel-death-toll-hamas-attack.html#:~:text=Israel%20revised%20its%20official%20estimated,Ministry%20said%20on%20Friday%20nig>

³ <https://www.nytimes.com/article/israel-gaza-hamas-what-we-know.html>

⁴ <https://news.un.org/en/story/2023/10/1142687>

According to the latest humanitarian update from the UN Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs (OCHA) on the crisis, over 1,000 individuals have been reported missing and are presumed to be trapped or deceased beneath the rubble. Shifa Hospital, the largest medical facility in Gaza, is currently attending to approximately 5,000 patients, significantly surpassing its usual capacity of around 700 patients.

As of Monday, the UN Spokesperson stated that the average number of people taking refuge in Gaza shelters is 4,400, which is approximately 2.5 times their designated capacity. In UNRWA classrooms, around 70 civilians are sharing limited space.

A fresh aid convoy, consisting of 20 trucks, entered Gaza from Egypt through the Rafah border crossing, as reported by the Egyptian Red Crescent, according to UN Spokesperson Stéphane Dujarric during a briefing in New York.

Dujarric emphasized that this convoy constituted merely four percent of the pre-crisis daily necessities for Gaza's population exceeding two million. This marked the third delivery since the crossing reopened on Saturday following extensive diplomatic efforts. Throughout the weekend, a total of 34 trucks transported aid from the UN and the Egyptian Red Crescent into the enclave. The UN underscores that, to meet the escalating humanitarian needs, a minimum of 100 aid trucks daily is imperative.

The United Nations has played a pivotal role in addressing the prolonged conflict between Israel and Palestine. Actively engaged in seeking a peaceful resolution, the UN has participated in diplomatic initiatives, peacekeeping operations, and the provision of humanitarian aid in the region. Various entities within the UN system, including the Security Council and General Assembly, have addressed different facets of the conflict.

Efforts to resolve the conflict often concentrate on promoting a two-state solution, allowing Israel and Palestine to coexist independently. The UN serves as a platform for international discussions, resolutions, and peacekeeping missions, facilitating negotiations between involved parties.

Consistently advocating for adherence to international law, the UN stresses the recognition of the needs and rights of both Israelis and Palestinians. UN agencies, notably the United Nations Relief and Works Agency for Palestine Refugees in the Near East (UNRWA), extend humanitarian assistance to Palestinian refugees and communities affected by the conflict.

The Group of Seven (G7) has called for "humanitarian pauses" in Israel's airstrikes to enable the urgent delivery of aid to the vulnerable Palestinian population in the Gaza Strip. The G7 statement aims to strike a balance, expressing criticism of Hamas's attacks and endorsing support for Israel while advocating for "urgent action" to address the critical needs of civilians in the besieged Gaza Strip. US Secretary of State Antony Blinken and the foreign ministers of Britain, Canada, France, Germany, Japan, and Italy emphasized their endorsement of "humanitarian pauses" to facilitate essential assistance, civilian movement, and the release of hostages in the region. They condemned "the rise in extremist settler violence committed against Palestinians," considering it "unacceptable, undermines security in the West Bank, and threatens prospects for lasting peace."

India maintains its official stance on the Israel-Palestine conflict, supporting a two-state solution that envisions Israel and Palestine as neighbouring entities living in harmony. India's stance is evident: they denounce terrorism but do not endorse indiscriminate retaliatory bombings.

Maintaining the current situation in the Israel-Palestine conflict poses significant challenges, and India has the potential to contribute positively by endorsing a peaceful resolution grounded in a two-nation theory. India should persist in its diplomatic initiatives, leveraging its global influence to encourage both Israel and Palestine to resume negotiations. It is crucial for India to sustain its role as a mediator, offering humanitarian aid to address immediate needs and alleviate suffering in areas affected by the conflict.

II. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This paper is based on secondary sources for the deep analysis of the conflict between Israel and Palestine. Secondary sources of information like newspapers, journals, and websites are used for the research.

III. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

During a ministerial meeting between India and the United States on November 10, India reiterated the necessity of a two-state solution to resolve the ongoing Israel-Palestinian crisis. The Foreign and Defence Ministers from both nations focused on the October 7 Hamas attack on Israel and called for the "immediate release" of individuals held hostage in the Gaza Strip. Notably, the discussions did not mention a ceasefire; instead, both India and the U.S. advocated for "humanitarian pauses" in the conflict.

"In light of the alarming terrorist attacks targeting Israel, the Ministers emphasized the solidarity of India and the United States with Israel in the fight against terrorism. They stressed the importance of adhering to international humanitarian law, especially in safeguarding civilians. The joint statement, following the '2+2' ministerial meeting, called for the prompt release of all remaining hostages," according to the statement.

Foreign Secretary Vinay Mohan Kwatra additionally conveyed that India had put forth the suggestion of a "two-state solution and the early resumption of dialogue" as a viable path to address the crisis.⁵

The sources used in this entire research paper are based through descriptive, very viable and trusted sources. Al-Jazeera is the foremost and the most prevalent source used in Gaza, which showcases the current happenings in the country. The Hindu is used for the off late affairs and the statements passed by the Indian officials and top diplomats.

IV. SUGGESTIONS & CONCLUSION

First things first, we need immediate humanitarian access to reach Gaza including crucial lifesaving supplies like water, food, fuel. United Nations facilities, hospitals, educational institutions, and medical centers should never be subjected to attacks. Emphasis was placed on the critical need for immediate humanitarian access to the enclave.

There is a urgency in International Mediation and Diplomacy. The involvement of International Bodies and encouragement in the active participation of international organizations such as the United Nations, the European Union, and regional entities in mediating and facilitating negotiations. Supporting the convening of multilateral forums that bring together key stakeholders, fostering dialogue and collaboration. Major countries like Saudi Arabia, Iran and other Arab countries call for a cease fire in the war to prevent further loss of property and damage.⁶

The most ideal is the two-State Solution for both Palestine and Israel, to Ensure that any proposed two-state solution addresses the security concerns and sovereignty of both Israel and Palestine. Recognition to promote mutual recognition between the two states, acknowledging each other's right to exist and thrive. Advocate for an immediate ceasefire to

⁵ <https://www.thehindu.com/news/national/gaza-crisis-india-bats-for-two-state-solution-during-talks-with-us/article67522472.ece>

⁶ <https://www.nytimes.com/2023/11/11/world/middleeast/iran-saudi-arabia-gaza-cease-fire.html>

halt violence and allow humanitarian organizations to provide critical aid to those affected. Protection of Civilians and to emphasize the importance of protecting civilians, including ensuring the safety of essential services like hospitals and schools. Addressing core issues like The Status of Jerusalem: Facilitate discussions on the status of Jerusalem, recognizing its significance to both Israelis and Palestinians, and explore potential solutions, such as shared sovereignty or international administration.

To also deal with refugee Issues and address the right of return for Palestinian refugees, considering feasible options that respect both the humanitarian needs and security concerns of all parties. Borders and Security to establish clear and agreed-upon borders, addressing security concerns through diplomatic agreements and international guarantees. Dialogue and People-to-People Initiatives such as Track II Diplomacy and promoting diplomacy, involving non-governmental actors and citizens in informal dialogues to build trust, and understanding.

